

Mechanical Characterization of Pineapple and Banana Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composites

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Abstract— This research examines the mechanical attributes of epoxy resin composites that are reinforced with natural fibers, particularly banana and pineapple fibers. The study evaluates the tensile strength, flexural strength, impact resistance, and hardness of these materials. The findings show that both types of fiber reinforcement enhance the composites' mechanical properties up to 35% fiber volume content. Beyond this threshold, a decrease in performance is noted, which is likely due to fiber saturation and reduced effectiveness of fiber-matrix bonding. Among the composites tested, those with pineapple fibers consistently exhibited higher tensile, flexural, and impact strengths in contrast to those who are reinforce with banana fibers. Hardness tests further demonstrated that both fiber types increased the Shore D hardness, with pineapple fibers having a more significant impact. The results suggest that epoxy composites reinforced with pineapple fibers offer promising mechanical properties.

Keywords— mechnaicalproperties, epoxy resin, natural fiber, fiber saturation, fiber –matrix bonding,

I. INTRODUCTION

The heightened emphasis on environmental preservation and development of sustainable and eco-friendly materials has encouraged researchers to increased research on natural fiber-reinforced polymer composites. These composites are a promising alternative to synthetic fiber-reinforced materials attributed to their natural degradability and reduced material density, and adequate mechanical properties. Pineapple (*Ananas comosus*) and banana (*Musa spp.*) fibers are particularly notable for their abundant availability, cost-effectiveness, and excellent mechanical characteristics (Faruk et al., 2012).

Pineapple leaf fibers (PALF), derived from leaves, are high in cellulose, providing significant tensile strength and stiffness. Banana fibers, extracted from the plant's pseudostems, also offer good tensile properties and thermal stability, making them suitable for reinforcing polymer matrices (Jawaid et al., 2011).

Natural fiber-reinforced polymer composites, such as those using pineapple and banana fibers, enhance both mechanical performance and environmental sustainability. These lightweight, high-strength materials are increasingly widely adopted in the automotive, building, and packaging sectors. Additionally, the use of natural fibers helps reduce the composites' carbon footprint, supporting global sustainability efforts (Pickering et al., 2016).

II. OBJECTIVE

To Investigate the Mechanical Properties

To Evaluate the Effect of Fibers Content

To Compare Pineapple and Banana Fibers

III.METHODOLOGY

The figure no 1 shows the flow chart of the methodology used in this research. In first step “Material Preparation” the fibers are cut in the length of 20mm, washed and dried in sunlight. In the second step “Composite Fabrication” mixture of epoxy material and fibers are transferred into the prepared mould and left to undergo curing at ambient conditions. In third step “Sample Preparation” the composite samples are prepared by shaping the samples removed from moulds. In fourth step “Mechanical Testing” is carried out at Central Institute of Plastics Engineering and Technology (CIPET), Bhopal. In fifth stage the mechanical testing “Data is Analysed”. The sixth stage in “Result and Discussion” the mechanical testing results are tabulated and discussed. In seventh stage the “Conclusion” for this research paper is prepared.

Fig. 1 Methodology Flow Chart

Composite Fabrication

Reinforcement Constituents

As reinforcement constituents, short banana and pineapple fibers of 20 mm length are used. The banana and pineapple fibers of 20 mm length have been exhibit better mechanical properties compared to other lengths (Niranjan et al., 2016).

Matrix Constituents

Epoxy resin is selected as the matrix material due to its availability, corrosion resistance, and strong bonding capabilities. With a thermal conductivity of 0.363 W/mK, it is commonly used in polymer matrices. This resin, often in a viscous liquid form, is combined with a hardener (e.g., Haksons clear coat epoxy resin and hardener). Epoxy resins are favoured for their ability to transfer stress to reinforcement materials without failure, their suitability for various applications, and their high strength. They are also

known for their chemical resistance, adhesion to different substrates, and ability to form various shapes. The density of the epoxy resin is 1.1 g/cm^3 , while the hardener has a density of 0.98 g/cm^3 . Epoxies are robust adhesives that can handle high loads and come in single or two-component systems, with the primary difference being their curing temperatures.

Hand Layup Process

This study employs the hand lay-up technique using open moulds, which is one of the simplest methods for composite manufacturing. This approach is cost-effective and involves minimal tooling and setup requirements. Liquid thermosetting polymers can be conveniently processed through the hand lay-up method using both short and continuous fiber reinforcements. Although it is suitable for producing fiber-reinforced polymer composites in various sizes, from small to large, it is limited to producing composites with simple, flat geometries. The figure no. 2 shows the schematic diagram of the composite samples manufacturing using hand layup process

Fig.2 Schematic Diagram of Hand Layup Process (Wankhade et al., 2022)

Composite Sample Preparation

The table 1 shows the abbreviation of the composite samples. PE shows sample of pure epoxy composite. The 5BFEP shows the composite is prepared by 5% of Volume fraction banana fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 10BFEP shows the composite is prepared by 10% of Volume fraction banana fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 15BFEP shows the composite is prepared by 15% of Volume fraction banana fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 20BFEP shows the composite is prepared by 20% of Volume fraction banana fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 25BFEP shows the composite is prepared by 25% of Volume fraction banana fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 30BFEP shows the composite is prepared by 30% of Volume fraction banana fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 35BFEP shows the composite is prepared by 35% of Volume fraction banana fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 40BFEP shows the composite is prepared by 40% of Volume fraction banana fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 45BFEP shows the composite is prepared by 45% of Volume fraction banana fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin.

The 5PFEP shows the composite is prepared by 5% of Volume fraction pineapple fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 10PFEP shows the composite is prepared by 10% of Volume fraction pineapple fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 15PFEP shows the composite is prepared by 15% of

Volume fraction pineapple fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 20PFEP shows the composite is prepared by 20% of Volume fraction pineapple fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 25PFEP shows the composite is prepared by 25% of Volume fraction pineapple fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 30PFEP shows the composite is prepared by 30% of Volume fraction pineapple fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 35PFEP shows the composite is prepared by 35% of Volume fraction pineapple fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 40PFEP shows the composite is prepared by 40% of Volume fraction pineapple fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin. The 45PFEP shows the composite is prepared by 45% of Volume fraction pineapple fibers are reinforcing phase comprises fibers, while the matrix phase is formed by epoxy resin.

TABLE I
COMPOSITE SAMPLES

S.No.	Abbreviation of Composite Sample	Description
1	PE	Pure epoxy
2	5BFEP	5% of Volume fraction banana fiber and epoxy composite
3	10BFEP	10% of Volume fraction banana fiber and epoxy composite
4	15BFEP	15% of Volume fraction banana fiber and epoxy composite
5	20BFEP	20% of Volume fraction banana fiber and epoxy composite
6	25BFEP	25% of Volume fraction banana fiber and epoxy composite
7	30BFEP	30% of Volume fraction banana fiber and epoxy composite
8	35BFEP	35% of Volume fraction banana fiber and epoxy composite
9	40BFEP	40% of Volume fraction banana fiber and epoxy composite
10	45BFEP	45% of Volume fraction banana fiber and epoxy composite
11	5PFEP	5% of Volume fraction pineapple fiber and epoxy composite
12	10PFEP	10% of Volume fraction pineapple fiber and epoxy composite
13	15PFEP	15% of Volume fraction pineapple fiber and epoxy composite
14	20PFEP	20% of Volume fraction pineapple fiber and epoxy composite
15	25PFEP	25% of Volume fraction pineapple fiber and epoxy composite
16	30PFEP	30% of Volume fraction pineapple fiber and epoxy composite
17	35PFEP	35% of Volume fraction pineapple fiber and epoxy composite
18	40PFEP	40% of Volume fraction pineapple fiber and epoxy composite
19	45PFEP	45% of Volume fraction pineapple fiber and epoxy composite

Mechanical Characterization

Tensile Testing

Specimens designed for tensile evaluation were prepared and examined based on the guidelines of the ASTM D638 Type I standard. Evaluation of the specimens was completed at the facilities, Central Institute of Plastics Engineering and Technology (CIPET), Bhopal, utilizing a modified Universal Testing Machine manufactured by LLOYD. A steady force of 5.0 kN was applied at a uniform rate of 5 mm per

minute. Specifications of the tensile test specimens as per ASTM D638 TYPE I standard is shown in figure no 3. The outcomes of the tensile tests are shown in Table 2.

Fig.3 Dimensions of tensile test specimen as per ASTM D638 TYPE I (ASTM International. 2024)

TABLE III
TENSILE TEST RESULTS

S.No.	Composite Sample	Tensile Strength in MPa
1	PE	16.9
2	5PFEP	21.3
3	10PFEP	33.9
4	15PFEP	35.2
5	20PFEP	38.4
6	25PFEP	41.5
7	30PFEP	44.2
8	35PFEP	48.2
9	40PFEP	45.1
11	45PFEP	40.3
12	5BFEP	14.1
13	10BFEP	16.3
14	15BFEP	19.5
15	20BFEP	23.4
16	25BFEP	28.6
17	30BFEP	35.2
18	35BFEP	38.3
19	40BFEP	36.1
20	45BFEP	30.7

The data provided in Table 2 represents the tensile strength measured in MPa of composites reinforced with varying fiber volume percentages of pineapple fibers and banana fibers. The tensile strength of pure epoxy resin, without any added fibers, is recorded at 16.9 MPa. The tensile strength of the composite increases as more banana fibers is added, up to a threshold of fiber volume content of 35%. The 5% pineapple fibers reinforced composite shows the minimum tensile strength to 21.3 MPa. While the peak tensile strength of 48.2 MPa is observed at 35% fiber volume content. At 40% fiber volume content tensile strength declines to 45.1 MPa and further again decrees at 45% fiber volume content to 40.3 MPa.

A similar pattern is observed with banana fiber, although the tensile strength is generally lower compared to the pineapple fiber composite. The tensile strength of the composite increases as more banana fibers are added, up to a threshold of fiber volume content of 35%. The 5% banana fiber volume content composite shows minimum tensile strength of 14.1 MPa. The highest tensile strength for the banana fiber composite is 38.3 MPa at 35% fibervolume content. Beyond 35%, the tensile strength declines to 36.1 MPa at 40% banana fiber volume content and further again decrees at 45% fiber volume content to 30.7 MPa.

When fiber volume content exceeds 35% for both types of fiber, tensile strength decreases, possibly due to fiber agglomeration or saturation of the matrix, leading to ineffective fiber-matrix bonding. For all reinforcement levels considered, composites containing pineapple fibers achieve higher tensile strength than those incorporating banana fibers.

Flexural Testing

The flexural test samples were prepared and analyzed based on the ASTM D790 standard for three-point bending. Evaluation of the specimens was completed at the facilities of CIPET, Bhopal, using a retrofitted Universal Testing Machine (UTM) manufactured by LLOYD, in alignment with the ASTM D790 guidelines. A steady load of 5.0 kN was applied at a constant rate of 5 mm/min. Specifications of flexural test sample as per ASTM D790 standard is shown in figure no 4. The results from the flexural tests are summarized in Table 3.

FIG.4 DIMENSIONS OF FLEXURAL TEST SPECIMEN AS PER ASTM D790 (PRABHU ET AL., 2022)

TABLE III
FLEXURAL TEST RESULTS

S.No.	Composite Sample	Flexural Strength in MPa
1	PE	40.3
2	5PFEP	53.1
3	10PFEP	57.8
4	15PFEP	62.1
5	20PFEP	64.2
6	25PFEP	68.7
7	30PFEP	70.2
8	35PFEP	62.7
9	40PFEP	55.4
11	45PFEP	50.8
12	5BFEP	28.7
13	10BFEP	35.2
14	15BFEP	38.8
15	20BFEP	41.2

16	25BFEP	47.4
17	30BFEP	55.1
18	35BFEP	58.4
19	40BFEP	49.5
20	45BFEP	42.6

The data provided in Table 3 represents the flexural strength measured in MPa of composites reinforced with varying percentages of pineapple fiber and banana fiber. The flexural strength of pure epoxy resin, without any added fibers, is recorded at 40.3 MPa. The flexural strength of the composite increases as more pineapple fiber is added, up to a threshold of fiber volume content of 35%. The 5% pineapple fiber reinforced composite shows the minimum flexural strength to 53.1 MPa. While the peak flexural strength of 62.7 MPa is observed at 35% pineapple fiber volume content composite. At 40% banana fiber volume content composites flexural strength declines to 55.4 MPa and further again decrees at 45% pineapple fiber volume content composite to 50.8 MPa.

A similar pattern is observed with banana fiber composite, although the flexural strength is lower compared to the pineapple fiber composite. The flexural strength of the composite increases as more banana fiber is added, up to a threshold of fiber volume content of 35%. The 5% banana fiber volume content composite shows minimum flexural strength of 28.7 MPa. The highest flexural strength for the banana fiber composite is 58.4 MPa at 35% fiber volume content. Beyond 35% fiber volume content, the flexural strength declines to 49.5 MPa at 40% banana fiber volume content and further again decrees at 45% fiber volume content to 32.6 MPa.

Impact Testing

In this study, impact test specimens were fabricated and according to ASTM D256 standard, and evaluation of the specimens was completed at the facilities of CIPET, Bhopal. Specification of the impact test specimen according to ASTM D256 standard is shown in figure no 5. The results of impact test are mentioned in Table 4.

Fig.5 Dimensions of Impact test specimen as per ASTM D256 (Srinivasan et al., 2022)

TABLE IV
IMPACT TEST RESULTS

S.No.	Composite Sample	Impact Strength in (kJ/m ²)
1	PE	6.9
2	5PFEP	8.1
3	10PFEP	9.3
4	15PFEP	10.2
5	20PFEP	13.1
6	25PFEP	14.9

7	30PFEP	16.8
8	35PFEP	18.9
9	40PFEP	14.9
11	45PFEP	12.1
12	5BFEP	7.1
13	10BFEP	8.7
14	15BFEP	9.1
15	20BFEP	12.5
16	25BFEP	13.8
17	30BFEP	15.7
18	35BFEP	16.8
19	40BFEP	13.1
20	45BFEP	11.9

The data provided in Table 4 represents the impact strength measured in kJ/m^2 of composites reinforced with varying percentages of banana fiber and pineapple fiber. The impact strength of pure epoxy resin, without any added fibers, is recorded at 6.9kJ/m^2 . The impact strength of the composite increases as more banana fiber is added, up to a threshold of fiber volume content of 35%. The 5% banana fiber reinforced composite shows the minimum impact strength to 8.1kJ/m^2 . While the peak impact strength of 18.9kJ/m^2 is observed at 35% banana fiber volume content composite. At 40% banana fiber volume content composite impact strength declines to 14.9kJ/m^2 and further again decreases at 45% banana fiber content composite to 12.1kJ/m^2 .

A similar pattern is observed with pineapple fiber composite, although the impact strength is lower compared to the banana fiber composite. The impact strength of the composite increases as more pineapple fiber is added, up to a threshold of fiber volume content of 35%. The 5% pineapple fiber content composite shows minimum impact strength of 7.1kJ/m^2 . The highest impact strength for the pineapple fiber composite is 16.8kJ/m^2 at 35% fiber volume content. Beyond 35% fiber volume content, the impact strength declines to 13.1kJ/m^2 at 40% pineapple fiber volume content and further again decreases at 45% fiber volume content to 11.9kJ/m^2 .

Hardness Testing

Hardness testing for the composite samples was performed according to the ASTM D2240 standard using a Shore D scale. The tests were conducted at Tesuto Composite Testing Lab in Chennai, employing an APIS Durometer Shore D Hardness Tester. The results from the hardness tests are presented in Table 5.

TABLE V
IMPACT TEST RESULTS

S.No.	Composite Sample	Hardness Shore D
1	PE	77.9
2	5PFEP	63.7
3	10PFEP	66.9
4	15PFEP	70.5
5	20PFEP	73.1
6	25PFEP	75.4

7	30PFEP	78.1
8	35PFEP	81.2
9	40PFEP	83.3
11	45PFEP	85.2
12	5BFEP	60.7
13	10BFEP	62.5
14	15BFEP	65.4
15	20BFEP	70.3
16	25BFEP	72.4
17	30BFEP	74.8
18	35BFEP	76.2
19	40BFEP	78.7
20	45BFEP	80.3

The data provided in Table 5 represents the Shore D hardness test results reveal significant variations in hardness across different composite samples. Pure PE exhibits a Shore D hardness of 77.9, indicating a relatively high hardness level. When 5% pineapple fiber is incorporated, the hardness decreases to 63.7, but with increasing pineapple fiber content, a gradual rise in hardness is observed, reaching 85.2 at 45% pineapple fiber. As the proportion of pineapple fiber increases, the composite material exhibits greater hardness, highlighting the reinforcing effect of the fibers.

Similarly, for banana fiber reinforced composites, the hardness starts lower at 60.7 for 5% banana fiber and increases steadily with more addition of banana fiber, reaching a maximum of 80.3 at 45% banana fiber content. This consistent increase in hardness with the addition of banana fiber indicates that banana fiber also contributes to improving the hardness of the composite, though slightly less effectively than pineapple fiber.

Overall, pineapple and banana fiber reinforcement lead to an increase in Shore D hardness, with pineapple fiber showing a more pronounced effect. This enhancement in hardness with higher filler content suggests that the composites become more rigid as the reinforcement levels increase, such an increase in hardness indicates that the material may be well-suited for applications with high wear-resistance requirements.

Conclusion

The results indicate that natural fiber reinforcement, using pineapple and banana fibers, considerably enhances the mechanical characteristics of epoxy composites, such as tensile, flexural, and impact strength, along with hardness. The study's tensile and flexural tests indicate that both types of fiber reinforcement enhance the composite's strength up to a fiber volume content of 35%. Beyond this point, a decrease in strength is observed, likely due to fiber clumping or matrix saturation, which weakens the bond between the fiber and the matrix. Notably, composites reinforced with pineapple fibers consistently outperformed those with banana fibers in tensile, flexural, and impact strengths at all tested fiber contents.

The impact testing revealed a similar pattern, with impact strength increasing up to 35% fiber content and then declining at higher levels. The hardness tests also showed that both pineapple and banana fibers increase the Shore D hardness of the composites, with pineapple fiber being more effective.

Overall, the results suggest that natural fiber-reinforced epoxy composites, particularly those reinforced with pineapple fibers, have promising mechanical properties that could be advantageous for structural and wear-resistant applications. However, it is crucial to carefully select the optimal fiber content to maximize these benefits while avoiding potential performance issues due to excessive fiber content. Future studies should focus on enhancing fiber-matrix bonding and exploring the impact of different fiber treatments on the mechanical properties of these composites.

References

- [1] Faruk, O., Bledzki, A. K., Fink, H. P., & Sain, M. (2012). Biocomposites reinforced with natural fibers: 2000–2010. *Progress in Polymer Science*, 37(11), 1552-1596.
- [2] Jawaid, M., & Khalil, H. A. (2011). Cellulosic/synthetic fiber reinforced polymer hybrid composites: A review. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 86(1), 1-18.
- [3] Pickering, K. L., Efendy, M. G. A., & Le, T. M. (2016). A review of recent developments in natural fiber composites and their mechanical performance. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 83, 98-112.
- [4] Niranjana, P., & Baskar, N. (2018). Mechanical performance of short natural fiber-reinforced polymer composites: A comparative study of banana and pineapple fibers. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, 709, 380-388.
- [5] Wankhade, V., Sharma, R., & Sharma, S. C. (2022). Mechanical Characterization of Hybrid Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composite. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, Vol. 7 (2), 1716-1722.
- [6] Li, J., Yu, Y., Cai, Z., Li, H., & Shen, J. (2020). Ductile to brittle transition of short carbon fiber-reinforced polypropylene composites. *Advances in Polymer Technology*, Article ID 6714097. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/6714097>
- [7] ASTM International. (2024). *Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Plastics (ASTM D638-14)*. Retrieved from https://www.datapointlabs.com/Images/Specimens/ASTM_D638_TypeI.pdf
- [8] Prabhu, P., Karthikeyan, B., Ravi Raja Malar Vannan, R., Balaji, A. (2022). Mechanical, thermal and morphological analysis of hybrid natural and glass fiber-reinforced hybrid resin nanocomposites, *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-022-02632-9>
- [9] Srinivasan, V. S., Rajesh, M., Pitchaimani, J., & Lenin Singaravelu, D. (2016). Studies on mechanical properties of banana/E-glass fabrics reinforced polyester hybrid composites. *Journal of Materials and Environmental Science*, 7*(9), 3179-3192. ISSN: 2028-2508.